

GUIDELINES FOR CULTIVATING YOUTHS FOR ADHERING HONEST BEHAVIORS IN THE AREA OF RANONG PROVINCE

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Abstract

To study human behavior, add significant meanings to improve the lives of human beings, especially for youth. Hence, studying behavior facilitates advancements in public health, organizational behavior management, and early childhood education. Like other psychological factors, honest behavior also has significant meanings in human life. However, to adhere to honest behavior the role of guidelines for youth cultivation is very important. Hence, the objective of the present study is to investigate the role of consistency, openness, and empowerment for adhering to honest behavior, especially in the youth of Ranong province, in the south of Thailand. To acquire the aim of the present study, a survey aimed to collect primary data from the 470 youth persons in Ranong province, was preferred. Then, this primary data was analyzed by using Partial Least Square (PLS). Results of the present study disclosed that increased value for consistency, openness and empowerment in the youth also increases the value of honest behavior in the youth. Thus, the present study plays a crucial role for the practitioners and for the youth especially in Ranong province to bring prominent changes in honest behavior.

Keywords: Consistency, openness, empowerment, awareness, and honest behaviors.

1. Introduction

Truthfulness is a capability of a person that helps to know the strength of his/her weaknesses and strengths (Bruzzone, 2021). Further, it is the fundamental factor that shapes the honest behavior of a person. Through truthfulness, honest behavior is formed that does not delude a person about his/her failures or successes. Instead, due to honest behavior, a person presents himself in a way that reflects what really, he/she is. Bringing honesty in behavior provides a base for trust in a relationship. Because in a relationship trust has significant importance. According to the present study, honest behavior is important especially for youth in Ranong province.

The young generation in Ranong is directly influenced by digital media and the content shown on the media. Social media also plays a significant role in the lives of youth, especially in Ranong. Hence, their behavior due to non-recommended and disreputable, unfair, and unethical content, has become deceptive, untrustworthy, untruthful, partial, and deceitful. Not only social media and the content they watch on their screen are responsible for their current behavior but other social factors such as bad companies, disreputable influential individuals are also responsible for the behavior of the youth. Hence, youth behavior especially in Ranong is totally against the values of the culture and religion of the people in the province. Hence, Ranong youth is facing various kinds of issues related to their behavior. Their current behavior is not suitable. Several factors influence youth behavior. However, lack of consistency, openness, empowerment, and awareness is the major factor that directly influences the behavior of the youth. Hence among all other factors consistency, openness, empowerment, and awareness are also responsible for the current behavior of the youth. According to the present study, the

increased value of consistency and openness in youth helps them to bring honesty in their behavior while more empowerment and awareness also promises positive changes in the youth behavior. The present study is a pioneer study that investigated the role of consistency, openness, empowerment, awareness on honest behavior of the youth, especially in Ranong province. Several studies explored the role of consistency and openness however, none of them have related with the honest behavior of the youth. Moreover, studies on empowerment and awareness are also available but they also have missed to investigate the role of honest behavior. It is also determined that the past literature is also missed to discuss the behavior of the youth of Ranong. Hence, the present study is a vital contribution to the body of the literature.

As it is evident from the literature that consistency in a job leads to increase the performance and value of the results gained from the job. Moreover, openness is key to improve the positivity in behavior. Furthermore, empowerment is one of the effective factors that promises quick and rapid changes that also help to develop behavior. And more awareness about a particular thing means more development for the thing. Hence, awareness about current behavior also helps a lot to increase the value of the current behavior. Therefore, the objective of the present study is to determine the role of consistency, openness, empowerment, and awareness on honest behavior of the youth, especially in Ranong province.

The present study also has a significant contribution to the literature. Because the present study explored the relationship between consistency, openness, empowerment, awareness, and honest behavior. Hence, the present study has both practical as well as theoretical contributions. Theoretically, the present study describes the relationship between consistency, openness, empowerment, awareness, and honest behavior. While practically the present study is more significant for the youth especially in Ranong province and the practitioners to boost the value of honest behavior.

2. Literature Review

Youth is considered a dynamic and important segment of the public of any country or region. For tremendous growth, it is mandatory to develop youth. Without proper development of youth, it is impossible to survive as a nation. Hence, investment in young people is always beneficial. There are many dimensions of a young person that need extra care however, according to the present study their behavior is one of the most significant dimensions that require more care, personal interest, and concern. Hence, Figure 1 shows the relationship between consistency, openness, empowerment, awareness, and honest behavior.

Figure 1: The theoretical framework of the study shows the relationship between consistency, openness, empowerment, awareness, and honest behaviors.

2.1 Consistency and Awareness

Consistency refers to one's ability to be affirmed, asserted, or insisted together without conflict, variance to something, or contradiction. A past study described that consistency is the name of preventing logical contradiction (Di Zio, 2021). Hence, consistency plays a significant role in various aspects of life. According to the present study, consistency is important to the awareness of youth, especially in the Ranong province of Thailand. Because the role of youth for a nation is considered as a backbone of the nation. Therefore, the present study investigated the role of consistency in the awareness of the youth. Results revealed that increasing the value of consistency in young people also increases their value of awareness. While a decrease in the value of consistency also results in a decrease in the value of awareness. Hence, it is enclosed that.

H1: Consistency has a positive influence on awareness.

2.2 Consistency and Honest Behavior

Consistency is like magic to honest behavior. Without consistency, any aspect of life is not effective as it can be with consistency. Consistency in behavior reflects the endurance of the behavior. Hence, behavior with consistency strengthens one's relationship with others. According to a past study, consistency adds significant meaning to forming a serious relationship (Izabel-Shen, Höger, & Jürgens, 2021). People at a young age go for experiments to build their behavior. Once, young people have adopted a behavior as per their wish and desire, now the role of consistency becomes more important. It is determined in the present study that young people especially in Ranong province, who have a consistent value of their honest behavior, normally enjoy an effective, successful, persuasive, and adequate lifestyle. On the other hand, the young people who still are experimenting or don't bring consistency in their honest behavior, the value of their behavior is comparatively low. Hence, it is encapsulated that.

H2: Consistency has a positive influence on honest behavior.

2.3 Openness and Awareness

Openness allows people to create fresh ideas, embrace new things, follow modern fashion, and experience the current version of the stuff. Such people are open-minded and new stuff attracts them. Hence, openness is to pursue creative endeavors, new experiences, and adventures. A prior study described that openness refers to the curiosity in a person's mind that provokes the person to seek out novelty (Abdullateef & Okonkwo, 2021). However, the present study determined that openness plays a significant role in the awareness of people especially those who are embracing openness at a young age, particularly in Ranong province. Results of the present study disclosed that the value of awareness in young people becomes more by embracing openness. While with the decrease in the value of openness in the young people also decrease the value of awareness of those young people. Hence, it is enclosed that.

H3: Openness has a positive influence on awareness.

2.4 Openness and Honest Behavior

Honesty refers to one's uprightness, truthfulness, frankness, fairness, and sincerity. It gives freedom from fraud or deceit. A prior study described honesty as a facet of moral character that signifies virtuous and positive attributes such as being trustworthy, fair, loyal, and sincere (Tanveer, Zeng, Irfan, & Peng, 2021). Hence, honesty is a positive aspect of life. According to the present study, people at a young age normally accept honest behavior however, they struggle with consistency and improvement in their honest behavior. Because there are many factors that influence youths' honest behavior. Openness is one of the major factors that influence youths' behavior. The results of the present study disclosed that increased value of openness in youth especially in Ranong province also increases the value of honest behavior of the youth. Hence, it is enclosed that.

H4: Openness has a positive influence on honest behavior.

2.5 Empowerment and Awareness

Empowerment provides motivation and encouragement to do a specified thing. A prior study described that empowerment creates more positive value for your current condition (PHAM THI, NGO, DUONG, & PHAM, 2021). Through empowerment, young people are able to complete their education, live a healthy lifestyle, and complete their desired or running projects. Moreover, it is the empowerment that helps young people to have full benefits of their rights. Results of the present study also revealed that young people having an increased value of empowerment, also have increased value for their awareness. While the young people with no or low value of empowerment live with a reduced value of their awareness. Hence, the value of the awareness of the young people especially in Ranong province changes with the change in the value of empowerment. Therefore, it is enclosed that.

H5: Empowerment has a positive influence on awareness.

2.6 Empowerment and Honest Behavior

According to Alatas (2017) “Youth is the hope of our future.” Hence, the improved behavior of youth is very important. There are several factors that directly impact the behavior of the youth. Empowerment is one of the effective factors that have a significant influence on behavior. A prior study revealed that empowerment gives opportunities to bring personal development such as personality development, behavior development, and character development (Kosholap et al., 2021). Furthermore, empowerment-oriented strategies in young people especially in Ranong province help to identify changes in their current behavior. Results of the present study revealed that increasing the value of empowerment-oriented strategies or empowering young people results in an increase in the value of honesty in their behavior. Thus, it is enclosed that.

H6: Empowerment has a positive influence on honest behavior.

2.7 Awareness and Honest Behavior

There are many factors that help to know the real value of an entity or person. Awareness about the entity or the person is one of the major factors that help to identify the actual values of various attributes of a person such as personality, character, and behavior (Huang & Qian, 2021). Hence, to make changes, or improvements, especially in behavior, the role of awareness is significant. When a young person has knowledge now, he/she can know what he/she can do to find the right direction or to make a wise decision. According to the present study, for a young person to bring honesty in his/her behavior initially it is mandatory to have awareness about the current value of his/her behavior. Results of the present study also revealed that young people without awareness about their behavior struggle to bring honesty into their behavior. It is also clear from the results of the present study that increasing the value of awareness of the young people about their behavior also increases the value of honesty in their behavior. Hence, it is enclosed that.

H7: Awareness has a positive influence on honest behavior.

H8: Awareness mediates the relationship between consistency and honest behavior.

H9: Awareness mediates the relationship between openness and honest behavior.

H10: Awareness mediates the relationship between empowerment and honest behavior.

3. Research Methodology

A research method is very important specially to get the required results. Hence, it is important to select an appropriate method. Among researchers, usually, three research methods named: qualitative research method, quantitative research method, and mixed-method are widely accepted that they use to achieve the results of their studies. However, the nature of the study determines which research method to opt. The nature of the present study is quantitative hence, a quantitative research method was opted to get the results of the present study.

After selecting the quantitative research method, a questionnaire was designed because the present study used a questionnaire survey to collect primary data. The questionnaire was distributed into three sections based on the nature of the questions in the questionnaire. The section of the questionnaire was containing the questions asked about the demographic information of the respondents such as respondents' name, age, qualification, sex, etc. In the second section of the questionnaire, the respondents were responsible to answer the questions asked about the key variables of the present study such as consistency, openness, empowerment, awareness, and honest behavior. In the last section of the questionnaire a five-point Likert scale starting from 1 as "Absolutely Yes" to 5 as "Absolutely No" was preferred containing 25 questions. Then, a sample size of the present study was selected based on the recommendation of Comrey and Lee (1992) who recommended that "sample having less than 50 participants will be observed to be a weaker sample; sample of 100 size will be weak; 200 will be adequate; sample of 300 will be considered as good; 500 very good whereas 1000 will be excellent." Thus, the present study selected a 1000 sample size which is excellent.

After the selection of sample size of the present study, the population of the present study was selected. The population of the present study includes young people from various communities such as young employees, university students, and literate labour working in various factories, without gender discrimination. The population of the present study was selected from various parts of Ranong province which is a wide area. Hence, the area cluster sampling approach was preferred because the area cluster sampling approach is suitable for a widespread population.

After collecting the basic contact information of the 1000 respondents from their concerning offices, the copies of the questionnaire were distributed among them via the Thai nation post service. A copy of the questionnaire along with a brief description of the objective of the present study was sent to the home address of each respondent. After 18 days of the questionnaire sent to the respondents, there were 335 responses received. Hence, a reminder message was sent to the phone number of the rest of the respondents. Hence, after 10 days of the reminder message, 200 more responses were received. Hence, after 28 days, there were 535 responses in total. 65 responses out of 535 were excluded because these 65 responses were partially filled. Hence, the rest 470 responses were considered as primary data for the present study. Then this primary data was analyzed by using PLS to achieve the objectives of the present study. All the measures and scales were used based on the previous literature.

4. Data Analysis

After hypotheses development it is mandatory to check the relationship to accept or reject the hypotheses. First of all, reliability and validity are examined which is considered by using Partial Least Square (PLS). Hence, Figure 2 shows outer model which highlighted the confirmatory factor analysis. Table 1 shows factor loadings, composite reliability (CR) and average variance extracted (AVE). The value of Factor loading, CR and AVE should be above 0.5, 0.7 and 0.5, respectively. Results in Table 1 shows that all the values meet the minimum threshold level. Discriminant validity is presented in Table 2 with the help of heterotrait-monotrait ratio of correlations (HTMT)_{0.9}.

Figure 2: P Measurement Model

Table 1: Factor Loadings, Cronbach' Alpha, CR and AVE

Variables	Items	Loadings	Alpha	CR	AVE
Awareness	AW1	0.646	0.890	0.924	0.715
	AW2	0.891			
	AW3	0.923			
	AW4	0.927			
	AW5	0.880			
Consistency	CY1	0.773	0.759	0.838	0.509
	CY2	0.675			
	CY3	0.739			
	CY4	0.699			
	CY5	0.678			
Empowerment	EP1	0.698	0.777	0.848	0.528
	EP2	0.640			
	EP3	0.710			
	EP4	0.760			
	EP5	0.814			
Honest Behavior	HB1	0.744	0.803	0.860	0.553
	HB2	0.724			
	HB3	0.801			
	HB4	0.765			
	HB5	0.676			
Openness	OP1	0.636	0.849	0.894	0.631
	OP2	0.667			
	OP3	0.879			
	OP4	0.894			
	OP5	0.858			

Table 2: HTMT0.9

	Awareness	Consistency	Empowerment	Honest Behavior	Openness
Awareness					
Consistency	0.813				
Empowerment	0.798	0.836			
Honest Behavior	0.783	0.829	0.808		
Openness	0.806	0.833	0.811	0.784	

4.1 PLS – SEMs Results

Figure 3 shows the structural model of the data of the present study. The relationship between awareness, consistency, empowerment, honest behavior, and openness was examined through PLS-SEM. T-value 1.96 is used to rejection and acceptance of the hypotheses of the present study. Table 3 shows the direct effect hypotheses. As per the results shown in Table 3, all the direct hypotheses are supported because t-value is above 1.96 and p-value is below 0.05. Table 4 shows mediating effects of the last three hypotheses of the present study. As per the results of Table 4 the last three mediation hypotheses are also supported.

Figure 3: Structural Model

Table 3. Direct Effects

Hypotheses	Beta	STDEV	T Values	P Values	Decisions
H1. Consistency -> Awareness	0.453	0.068	6.675	0.000	Supported
H2. Consistency -> Honest Behavior	0.447	0.073	6.127	0.000	Supported
H3. Openness -> Awareness	0.234	0.079	2.972	0.003	Supported
H4. Openness -> Honest Behavior	0.075	0.021	3.571	0.000	Supported
H5. Empowerment -> Awareness	0.171	0.075	2.284	0.023	Supported
H6. Empowerment -> Honest Behavior	0.152	0.064	2.362	0.019	Supported
H7. Awareness -> Honest Behavior	0.182	0.058	3.155	0.002	Supported

Table 4: Mediating Effects

Hypotheses	Beta	STDEV	T Values	P Values	Decisions
H8. Consistency -> Awareness -> Honest Behavior -> Honest Behavior	0.083	0.018	4.611	0.000	Supported
H9. Openness -> Awareness -> Honest Behavior -> Honest Behavior	0.076	0.022	3.454	0.000	Supported
H10. Empowerment -> Awareness -> Honest Behavior -> Honest Behavior	0.072	0.025	2.88	0.000	Supported

5. Discussion and Conclusion

The first hypothesis of the present study is: “consistency has a positive influence on awareness.” Dressler and Paunovic (2021) concluded that consistency is a valuable factor that helps to improve strategies and increases the impact of actions, decisions, and jobs. Further, Moriarty and Wilson (2022) also proved that the role of consistency in policymaking is very important because through consistency process of policymaking becomes more result-oriented and promises an effective policy. Thus, previous is literature also evident that consistency is an important factor that has significant impact on awareness.

The second hypothesis of the present study is: “consistency has a positive influence on honest behavior.” According to a past study conducted by Diller, Lorenz, Schneider, and Sureth (2021) disclosed that consistency plays a vital role in a process, as inconsistent notices by tax collecting authorities to the taxpayer, changed the behavior of taxpayer and after a time period, the taxpayers were not ready to pay their taxes, however, before inconsistency, they were regularly paying their taxes. Hence, it is clear that consistency brings positive changes to one’s behavior.

The third hypothesis of the present study is: “openness has a positive influence on awareness.” Describing behavioral intention in the International Congress of Advanced Technology and Engineering, Ahmed and Abdullah (2021) concluded that an open-minded approach helps to adopt a behavior that facilitated to increase in awareness. Further, openness is basically due to the curiosity of the mind about new experiences, modern theories, new things, and fresh knowledge about a particular thing, which increases awareness (Tan et al., 2021). Hence, it is clear from the past literature that openness adds significant positive meanings to the awareness of people.

The fourth hypothesis of the present study is: “openness has a positive influence on honest behavior.” According to previous literature, open-minded people are normally creative, intellectually curious, and imaginative (Cheng, 2021; Crider, 2021; Marshall, Keville, Cain, & Adler, 2021; Onyeocha, 2021). Open-minded people often try to explore new things, even when they go for eat a dish, they order for a different dish just aiming to find out the new taste, hence, with openness, such people are true and honest to meet their curious mind. Thus, it is obvious from the results of the present study and past literature that openness has a significant positive influence on the honest behavior of young people.

The fifth hypothesis of the present study is: “empowerment has a positive influence on awareness.” Safaeian, Tavakolifard, and Roohi (2022) concluded that the value of the awareness of the nurses of a hospital in Isfahan increases when they are empowered. Moreover, empowerment helps citizens to continue or increase the speed of work (Anggraeni, Hidayat, Yunani, Syafari, & Sompaa, 2021). Additionally, it is an empowerment that helps youth to develop their awareness about their leadership skills, gain work experience, and learn the importance of helping (Akter, Nayeem, & Didar, 2021). Hence, it is clear from the past literature that more empowerment promises more awareness.

The sixth hypothesis of the present study is: “empowerment has a positive influence on honest behavior.” Khan et al. (2021) through the results of their study agreed that increasing the value of empowerment of the employees brings more honesty in their behavior. A past study based on education and community health described that school students with more empowerment were more honest with their behavior, however, decreasing the value of empowerment also results in a decrease in the honesty of the students. Hence, it is also from the past literature that empowerment has a significant positive influence on honest behavior.

The seventh hypothesis of the present study is: “awareness has a positive influence on honest behavior.” Sugiarti, Rusmawati, and Yalestyarini (2021) concluded that a mother's awareness of her baby helps to develop the behavior of her baby. Further, it is also clear from the past literature that the behavior of university students in Sydney improved when the level of their awareness was positively changed (Islam, Dias, & Huda, 2021). Hence, it is clear from the past literature that awareness has significant positive effects on the honest behavior of young people. The last three hypotheses of the present study describe the mediating role of awareness. Awareness mediates the relationship between consistency, openness, empowerment, and honest behavior.

6. Implications

The present study provides various insights for young people and other practitioners while identifying the guidelines for youth cultivation. It is important because it emphasizes various factors affecting the honest behavior of young people, especially in Ranong province. The ultimate objective of the present study is to investigate the influence of consistency, openness, and empowerment on the awareness and honest behavior of young people. Hence, the present study is important for the youth and the practitioners aiming to improve their awareness and honest behavior.

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